

Effect of Local Government Administration on Rural Development: A Study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government Areas in Enugu State

¹Professor Eze, Fred O., ²Ubosi, Francisca Akunna, ³Mbah, Paulinus Chigozie PhD

^{1,2}Department of Public Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

³Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Accepted: September 12th, 2022

Published: September 30th, 2022

Citations - APA

Eze, F. O., Ubosi, F. A., & Mbah, P. C. (2022). Effect of Local Government Administration on Rural Development: A Study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government Areas in Enugu State. *International Journal of Economics and Public Policy*, 6(3), 1-22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7150610>

The study evaluated the effect of Local government administration on rural development: a study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas in Enugu State. The specific objectives are to: examine the extent Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government councils have enhanced primary Health care in their council areas; ascertain the performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas in the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their councils' areas and examine the extent of agricultural development by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas. The actual population was six hundred and two staff (602). The population of the study was drawn from the entire members of the local government staff and, executives of the town union leaders and selected individuals. The sample size of 225 was drawn using Freund and William's formula at 5 percent error margin. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. A total of two hundred and twenty-five (225) copies of questionnaire were distributed while two hundred and twenty-two (222) copies of questionnaire were returned. Z – test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings indicated that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas had negative and positive effect on the primary Health care in their council areas $Z(95, n = 222) = -.265 < .374, p > 0.05$. Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas had positive effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their councils' areas, $Z(95, n = 222) = .252 < .361, p < 0.05$ and the agricultural development had positive effect in Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas, $Z(95, n = 222) = .297 < .362, p < 0.05$. The study concluded that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas had negative and positive effect on the primary Health care in their council areas while Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas had positive effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads and agricultural development in their council areas. The study recommended that the local government authorities should be more proactive and ensure provision of budget for health care of the people in their local government council areas.

←
ABSTRACT

Keywords: Local government Administration; Rural Development, Primary Healthcare; Agricultural Development

Introduction

One of the recurring problems of Nigeria's third-tier system is the declining performance of local government administration in terms of rural development, which is marked by annual budget deficits and inadequate funds for significant projects in the rural areas. The expectation is that as a third tier of government; local government councils should act as catalysts for sustainable development at the grassroots level (Oduola, Olasunkanmi, Sawaneh, and Ogunbela, 2019). The local government in Nigeria was established for the purpose of rendering services and supplying amenities to the people in both rural and urban areas according to the guidelines for local government reforms in 1976. By extension, the same conditions apply to local governments in Enugu state which were created on 27th August 1991. The Federal government cannot provide all the amenities at the rural areas by themselves, but this can only be done by the people elected at the grassroots. This does not stop the federal government from implementing its programmes by providing some social amenities, such as construction of roads, provision of pipe borne water, hospitals, good education for youths, electricity etc. All these social amenities are made available from the revenue generated from the people (Olorungbemi, 2015).

Local government is an essential instrument for the performance of certain basic services which can best be decided upon and administered on the intimate knowledge of the needs, conditions and peculiarities of the area concerned. (Anorom, 2012). One of the major justifications for local government in modern times is that it promotes participation by local communities in governmental activities as well as serving as machinery for harnessing local level efforts for development purposes (Scharticles, 2014). Local government is a public sector organization with assigned functions and responsibilities, administrative structure and financial arrangements for maintaining both itself and rendering its statutorily assigned functions to its citizens. This way, the generic centrality of finance to organizational performances also applies to local governments (Idahosa, & Nchuchuwe, 2005).

In theory, local government is a unit of government with defined powers and authority, and relative autonomy. The functional areas for local government included in the fourth schedule of the constitution are: provision and maintenance of health services; agricultural and natural resource development; provision and maintenance of primary, adult and vocational education; and other functions as may be conferred on it by the State House of Assembly, (Ozhu and Paul, 2016). Over the years, it has been observed that increasingly, most Local Governments across the country are unable and or unwilling to satisfactorily perform their critic roles in rural developments here. Therefore, the present situation prompts the need to evaluate local government administration in rural development. A study of Enugu east and Isi-Uzo Local government areas in Enugu state.

Statement of Problem

Local governments are the nearest government to the people at the grassroots in Nigeria. They are strategically located to play a pivotal role in national development. Since they are responsible for the governance of about 70 percent of the population of Nigeria, they are in advantaged position to articulate the needs of the majority of Nigerians and formulate strategies for their realization. It is a fact that the extent to which a rural development goal can be accomplished will largely depend on the local government administration that drives it.

The problem however, is that most local government councils in Enugu State like in many other states lack the capacity or political will to raise corollary funds to its statutorily allocated fund from the states and federal governments as required by fiscal federalism which she operates. This is due to the fact that much of the internally generated revenue is embezzled by political office holders. The bureaucrats at all levels are not left in actuating corruption and other related vices which have largely contributed to the paucity of funds in the local government councils. However, the abysmal way and manner by which local government authorities mismanage funds due to corruption of, some personnel make a mockery of local government administration in Nigeria. Additionally, avoidance of tax by the private sector organisations and rich individuals raises a fundamental challenge to revenue generation and local government administration in Nigeria, thereby causing the local government to underperform in the areas of effective Primary health care, constructed local roads, and local parks and recreation services.

Local government administration has been considered as a significant factor in the economic development of any nation. It serves as a life wire of every community which helps them to attain its goals. Thus, the above challenges of local governments' administration needed a redress. The apparent abysmal performance of local governments

across the country in the rural developments is worrisome as they constitute the third-tier government which are closer to 70 percent of Nigeria population and would generally affect the development of the country. Based on the above background, the study evaluates Local government administration in rural development: a study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas in Enugu state.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of Local government administration on rural development: A study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas in Enugu state. The specific objectives are to:

- I. Examine the extent Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government councils have enhanced primary Health care in their council areas.
- II. Ascertain the performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas in the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas.
- III. Examine the extent of agricultural development by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- I. To what extent have Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government councils enhanced primary Health care in their council areas?
- II. What is the performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas in the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas?
- III. To what extent is the agricultural development by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

- I. Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas have not contributed significantly to enhancement of primary health care in their council areas
- II. Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas has no significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas
- III. There is no significant development in agricultural by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas

Significance of the Study

The study on Local government administration in rural development will be of great benefit to the following stakeholders:

Nation/Country: countries that have independent local government that can generate and consciously utilize their generated revenue are prone to development. The study will help the federal and state government to make provision of separate account for local government rather than the joint local-state account in order to conduct proper evaluation of performance.

Local Governments: the study will benefit both the executive and legislative arm of the local governments by unveiling areas of rural development and probably have their autonomy as the third-tier of government without dependency on the state offer due to the joint account.

Organizations: other public and private organizations will benefit from the study by understanding the importance of rural development and need to have diverse means of generating revenue.

Researchers: the study will serve as a basis and empirical resource for prospective researchers that would like to assess rural development in other states with respect to local government.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on the effect of Local government administration on rural development: a study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas in Enugu state. The local council issues are: medical centres, construction of local roads, and agricultural extensions. The time coverage of the study is 2019– 2022

Limitations of the study

The main limitation experienced was that most respondents considered some information as confidential and did not want to reveal everything. However, confidentiality and protection of information was assured to the respondents. Information was coded to avoid direct reference to particular individuals.

Review Of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Local Government

A local government is a form of public administration which, in a majority of contexts, exists as the lowest tier of administration within a given state. The organization of local governments varies depending on the state. However, all local governments derive their authority from the state in which they are located (Ashley, 2020). Local government may be loosely defined as a public organization authorized to decide and administer a limited range of public policies within a relatively small territory which is a subdivision of a regional or national government. Local government is at the bottom of a pyramid of governmental institutions, with the national government at the top and intermediate governments (states, regions, provinces) occupying the middle range (Palliser, 2020). Nigeria has 774 local government areas (L.G.As). Each local government area is administered by a Local Government Council consisting of a chairman who is the Chief Executive of the LGA, and other elected members who are referred to as Councillors. Local governments are created with the ultimate goal of bringing government closer to the people at the grassroots. In Nigeria, the local government reforms aimed both to accelerate development and to enable the local population participates and holds those in power accountable for their governance roles.

Components of Local Government Administration

The following are the components of local government administration employed for the study;

Primary Health Care

Primary health care, or PHC, refers to "essential health care" that is based on scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology. This makes universal health care accessible to all individuals and families in a community (Packard, 2016). PHC initiatives allow for the full participation of community members in implementation and decision making. "PHC is a whole-of-society approach to health that aims at ensuring the highest possible level of health and well-being and their equitable distribution by focusing on people's needs and as early as possible along the continuum from health promotion and disease prevention to treatment, rehabilitation and palliative care. The Nigerian health care has suffered several down-falls. Despite Nigerian's strategic position in Africa, the country is greatly underserved in the health care sphere. Health facilities (health centers, personnel, and medical equipment's) are inadequate in this country, especially in rural areas. While various reforms have been put forward by the Nigerian government to address the wide-ranging issues in the health care system, they are yet to be implemented at the state and local government area levels (Osain, 2011).

Nigeria as a federation of three tiers of governments (federal, state and local) share responsibilities for provision of health services, the federal government is largely responsible for providing policy, planning and technical assistance, coordinating state-level implementation of the National Health Policy and establishing health management information systems. PHC requires governments at all levels to underscore the importance of action beyond the health sector in order to pursue a whole-of government approach to health, including health-in-all-policies, a strong

focus on equity and interventions that encompass the entire life-course (WHO, (2021). In addition, the federal government is responsible for disease surveillance, drug regulation, vaccine management and training health professionals. It is also responsible for the management of teaching, psychiatric and orthopedic hospitals and some medical centers. The responsibility for the management of health facilities and programmes is shared by the State Ministries of Health, State Hospital Management Boards and the LGAs.

The Construction and Maintenance of Local Feeder Roads in the Council Areas

A local road or residential street primarily serves as access to a farm, residence, business, or other abutting property. Some such roads properly include geometric design and traffic control features more typical of collectors and arterials to encourage the safe movement of through traffic. On these roads, the through traffic is local in nature and extent rather than regional, intrastate, or interstate. Local roads serve primarily to provide access to the traffic emanating from the properties and discharge them onto collectors. They serve a minor role in the classification system and usually have low traffic. On Local streets speed is usually kept low due to the frequent movements of children and adults both in the residential area. Buses and heavy vehicles are less expected on local streets (Haseeb, 2017).

Agricultural Development

Nigeria Agricultural Extension policy edict of 1992, directed the states’ Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) to establish management committees at the zonal levels with Local Government Agricultural Department (LGAD). The primary objective is to create link between ADP and LGAD for implementing agricultural and rural development projects in the zone. These activities of extension can be made more effective and efficient in the atmosphere of inter-organizational relationship with governmental authority that is closer to the local people. Besides, constructing access roads, provision of water, storage facilities, processing units, and linking farmers to market and source credit has been identified as added functions of extension as stated by Enugu State Agricultural Development Programme.

Joint participatory agricultural extension project implementation was also identified as area of strong linkage of ADP with LGAD. This shows that ADP engages LGAD in extension project implementation. This could be to garner more presence and coverage among clientele, as most extension projects are time bound. And hence, the services of more personnel could speed up implementation. Joint training workshop for farmers, staff and other stakeholders in extension was enlisted as area of linkage of ADP with LGAD. This agrees with the core drive of every extension effort in which emphasis is often placed on mainstreaming stakeholders in programme initiation, implementation and evaluation which could engender sustainability of intervention programmes, (Ugwuoke, and Attamah, 2019).

Conceptual Framework

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Researcher’s compilation

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Public expenditure theory and Structural functional theory. The study was anchored on Structural functional theory. Structural Functionalism is a sociological theory that explains why society functions the way it does by emphasizing on the relationships between the various social institutions that make up society. Social structures give shape to our human lives.

Public Expenditure Theory

Public expenditure means the expenditure on the developmental and non-developmental activity such as construction of roadways and dams, and other activity. The theory of public expenditure by Wagner & Buchanan (1978) maintains that there is a functional relationship between the growth of an economy and government activities. According to him, Government sector grows faster than the economy when there is an increase in public expenditure. Though, Peacock and Wiseman (1979), reveal that public expenditure does not increase in a smooth and continuous manner, rather in step like fashion. As sometimes, some social or other disturbances creates a need to increase public expenditure which the existing public revenue cannot meet.

Structural-Functional Theory

Structural functionalism, or simply functionalism, is "a framework for building theory that sees society as a complex system whose parts work together to promote solidarity and stability". Functionalism grew out of the writings of English philosopher and biologist, Hebert Spencer (1820–1903), who saw similarities between society and the human body. The parts of society that Spencer referred to were the social institutions or patterns of beliefs and behaviors focused on meeting social needs, such as government, education, family, healthcare, religion, and the economy. Each social structure has social functions, or consequences for the operation of society as a whole. Spencer referred to the social institutions, or patterns of beliefs and behaviors focused on meeting social needs, such as government, education, family, healthcare, religion, and the economy. One of the key ideas in Structural Functionalism is that society is made-up of groups or institutions, which are cohesive, share common norms, and have a definitive culture.

Émile Durkheim, another early sociologist, applied Spencer's theory to explain how societies change and survive over time. Durkheim believed that society is a complex system of interrelated and interdependent parts that work together to maintain stability (Durkheim 1893), and that society is held together by shared values, languages, and symbols. He believed that to study society, a sociologist must look beyond individuals to social facts such as laws, morals, values, religious beliefs, customs, fashion, and rituals, which all serve to govern social life. In relation to the present study, Structural functional theory is an orientation that focuses on structure the patterning of roles, the form of institutions, and the overall articulation of institutions in a society and seeks to explain these structures in terms of their functions contributions to the stability and persistence of societies.

Empirical Review

Local Government Administration on Primary Health Care

Dangmei & Sing (2018) An Empirical Assessment of Primary Health Care Quality Services and Its Effect on Patient Satisfaction in Anuppur District, Madhya Pradesh. There is limited evidence on the quality of primary health care provision in India especially in the rural areas. It has been found that the death rate and the infant mortality rate in rural areas of Madhya Pradesh are quite high as compared to other states. Therefore, if government policy is to revitalize the primary care system, a basic understanding of the quality of services currently provided is a prerequisite. This study attempts to assess the quality of care and patient satisfaction in the primary health care services provided in the rural section of Anuppur District. This study also aimed at exploring the relationship and effect of quality of care on patient satisfaction. This study will also help the primary health care providers and policy maker to further enhance the quality of care and patient satisfaction in the Anuppur District (M.P). Data were analyzed from outpatients from various primary health care centres using descriptive statistics and SPSS 23. Findings indicated that the level of quality of care and patient satisfaction is medium or average and the results also showed that quality of care has a significant correlation with a mild effect on patient satisfaction.

Oserei & Uddin (2019) the myth and reality of government expenditure on primary health care in Nigeria: Way forward to inclusive growth. The health sector remains a vital tool for sustainable development of any nation and therefore investment in this sector cannot be overemphasized. The present state of Primary Health Care (PHC) system in Nigeria is alarming, with only about 20% out of the 30,000 PHC facilities relatively distributed throughout the 774 Local Government Areas (LGAs) across Nigeria working partially. This study examines government expenditure on primary health care in Nigeria as well as its relations to real national output within the period 1980 to 2015 using secondary data and the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) econometric technique. The results of the model used revealed government health expenditure to be efficacious for economic growth, and for the well-functioning of primary health care in Nigeria. Nonetheless, such efficacy duly was also understood to be limited in three select aspects: funding/financing strategy, personnel/manpower quality and mobilization, and implementation framework.

Espinosa-Gonzalez, Delaney, Marti & Darzi (2019) the impact of governance in primary health care delivery: a systems thinking approach with a European panel. The purpose of this study is to analyse the interactions between PHC functions and their impact in PHC delivery, particularly in providers' behaviour and practice organisation. Following a systems thinking approach with data obtained through a three-round European Delphi process, we developed a framework that captures the interactions between PHC functions by analysing correlations between PHC characteristics of participating countries, how actors involved shaped these interactions by identifying the actor and level of devolution (or fragmentation) in the analysis, and their potential effect on care delivery by exploring panellists' opinions. A total of 59 panellists from 24 countries participated in the first round and 76% of the initial panellists (22 countries) completed the last round. Findings show correlations between governance, financing and regulation based on their degree of decentralisation. This is supported by panellists, who agreed that the actors involved in health system governance determine the type of PHC financing and regulation and this may impact care delivery and outcomes. Governance in our framework is an overarching function whose impact in PHC delivery is mediated through the degree of decentralisation of PHC financing and regulation. The application of this approach in policy implementation assessment intends to uncover limitations due to poor accountability and commitment to shared objectives. Its application in the design of health strategies helps foresee (and prevent) undesired or unexpected effects of narrow interventions. This approach will assist in the development of the realistic and long-term policies required for health systems strengthening.

The Construction and Maintenance of Local Feeder Roads in the Council Areas

Suleiman, Abul and Setyawan (2020) The Empirical Review of Critical Success Factors on the Causes of Delay in Road Constructions Projects in the GCC Countries. The aim of this study is to identify the critical success factors on the delays of road constructions in the GCC countries and their effects on project delivery in Arab countries. Towards the achievement of the objectives the study used the empirical literature from all relevant online sources and data based as many as possible. The findings of this study have summarized and shortlisted the success factors in the two categories such as internal and external factors have caused to be influenced to delay of road construction in the Arab regions. However, in the category of internal factors, there are 63 factors shortlisted from seven groups of factors which has revealed to effects on the delay of road constructions especially, the consultant related factors, and the contractor related factors, designed related factors, client-related factors, labor- related factors, material related issues, equipment-related issues respectively. The present study also concluded the effects of the above factors which have delay road constructions through increasing of cost and overrun it, taken over time, creating of disputes, going for lawsuits, finally happing of abandon of projects.

Lendra, Wlbowo and Hatmoko (2020) Literature Review on Energy Consumption in Road Construction Projects Literature Review on Energy Consumption in Road Construction Projects. The aims of this study are to conduct a literature review to determine the extent of the previous research that have been carried out, as well as the consumption of energy in the construction projects. The results will be used as a basis for developing critical thinking and conceptual frameworks to fill the research gaps and provide novelty for further research. The study was conducted using a qualitative bibliometric analysis method by identifying selected academic publications from Scopus database with the use of VOSviewer software to process the data. The results of this study indicate that there is an opportunity to conduct research in order to develop energy optimization models for green and sustainable road construction projects from the design, construction, operation and maintenance stages.

Deep, Banerjee, Dixit, and Vatin (2022) Critical Factors Influencing the Performance of Highway Projects: An Empirical Evaluation. Since highways are the backbone of a nation, the purpose of this study is to measure the criticality of the factors that influence the performance of highway projects. A survey instrument was prepared and distributed to 185 project managers. To achieve the aim of the study, exploratory factor analysis was used and the standard factor loading was the criteria to measure the criticality. From the analysis, it was identified that the factors were grouped under four categories: (a) Execution constraints (b) Operational factors, (c) Stakeholder and political constraints, (d) Design Constraints. Further, it was concluded that the complexity of the sub-contractor's performance, frequent modification in alignment, project design, loopholes in safety, and ambiguities in specifications are the main factors that impact the performance of highway projects.

Local Government Administration on the Agricultural Development

Nwalieji and Igbokwe (2011), conducted a study on the Role of Local Governments in Agricultural Development in Nigeria: A Review, In Nigeria, agriculture is in the concurrent list and therefore, Local Governments by law have roles to play in agricultural development. The paper relies heavily on literature and participant observation. The failure of LG to perform its roles credibly is attributed among others to gross mismanagement and embezzlement of available fund, lack of financial autonomy, high level of corruption, general indiscipline among the workers, inadequacy of skilled workers, problems of participation and involvement, misplaced priority, poor job description of staff, absence of staff training and contacts with farmers. It is suggested that LGs should look inwards for improved IGR in order to make them financially self-reliant; linkages between LGC and ADP and other agricultural projects and programmes should be strengthened in order to foster development; bottom-up approach should be adopted in the linkage between LG and farmers for effective rural community involvement and participation in major decisions that affecting them; and there should be cost sharing by the three tiers of government in funding of extension at the LGA level and this could be done by legislation.

Gyanden (2015) conducted a study on the role of extension services in reduction of biomass burning in Okpokwu Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Nigeria is an agrarian country, over 65% of her population engages in agriculture; however the practice of biomass burning is threatening both the soil nutrients and human life. The study investigated the role of extension services in reducing biomass burning in Okpokwu local government area of Benue State, Nigeria. Primary data for the study were gathered with the use of structured questionnaire administered on 145 respondents selected randomly from five council wards that make up the study area. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The results of the findings revealed that 49.7% practised biomass burning for farming purposes, 37.9% biomass burning make soil prone to erosion, 33.1% extension services carried out public enlightenment on the dangers of biomass burning, 54.5% of the respondents stated that face-to-face contact was employed by extension agents in reaching the rural farmers, The result of analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that there was significant difference between the frequency of extension visit and the rate of information disseminated across the council wards in reducing biomass burning at 1%.

Ugwuoke and Attamah (2019) conducted a study to assess the inter-organizational relationship between the agricultural development programme (ADP) and the local government agricultural department (LGAD) in implementing participatory extension policy in Southeast, Nigeria. Two sets of questionnaires were used in collecting data from purposively selected 260 staff of the ADP and LGAD personnel involved in the execution of agricultural extension projects of the two agencies. Data were presented and analysed using descriptive statistics. Greater proportion (41.5%) of the ADP staff and LGAD personnel were within the age range of 40-49 years. About 87% of ADP staff and 90% of LGAD personnel were males. There was existence of formal and informal linkage between the two agencies that should be strengthened by governmental effort for more extension coverage.

Table 1: Summary of the Review of Related Literature

S/N	Author(s)	Year	Area of study	Title	Methodology	Findings
1	Nwalieji and Igbokwe	2011		Role of Local Governments in Agricultural Development in Nigeria: A Review	Survey design	The failure of LG to perform its roles credibly is attributed among others to gross mismanagement and embezzlement of available fund, lack of financial autonomy, high level of corruption, general indiscipline among the workers, inadequacy of skilled workers, problems of absence of staff training and contacts with farmers.
2	Gyanden	2015	Nigeria	The role of extension services in reduction of biomass burning in Okpokwu Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria	Descriptive and inferential statistics	The result of analysis of variance showed that there was significant difference between the frequency of extension visit and the rate of information disseminated across the council wards in reducing biomass burning at 1%
3	Dangmei & Sing	2018	Anuppur District, Madhya Pradesh	An Empirical Assessment of Primary Health Care Quality Services and Its Effect on Patient Satisfaction in Anuppur District, Madhya Pradesh	Descriptive Statistics	Findings indicated that the level of quality of care and patient satisfaction is medium or average and the results also showed that quality of care has a significant relationship with a mild effect on patient satisfaction
4	Espinosa-Gonzalez, Delaney, Marti & Darzi	2019	Europe	The impact of governance in primary health care delivery: a systems thinking approach with a European panel	Correlations Analyses	Findings show correlations between governance, financing and regulation based on their degree of decentralisation
5	Ugwuoke, and Attamah	2019	Nigeria	the inter-organizational relationship between the agricultural development programme and the local government agricultural department (LGAD) in implementing participatory extension policy in Southeast, Nigeria	Descriptive Statistics	Greater proportion (41.5%) of the ADP staff and LGAD personnel were within the age range of 40-49 years. About 87% of ADP staff and 90% of LGAD personnel were males. There was existence of formal and informal linkage between the two agencies that should be strengthened by governmental effort for more extension coverage.

6	Oserei & Uddin	2019	Nigeria	The myth and reality of government expenditure on primary health care in Nigeria: Way forward to inclusive growth	Ordinary Least Square (OLS) econometric technique	The results of the model used revealed government health expenditure to be efficacious for economic growth, and for the well-functioning of primary health care in Nigeria
7	Lendra, Wlbowo & Hatmoko	2019		Literature Review on Energy Consumption in Road Construction Projects	Qualitative Bibliometric Analysis	The results of this study indicate that there is an opportunity to conduct research in order to develop energy optimization models for green and sustainable road construction projects from the design, construction, operation and maintenance stages.
8	Suleiman, Abul & Setyawan	2020	Arab	The Empirical Review of Critical Success Factors on the Causes of Delay in Road Constructions Projects in the GCC Countries	Survey Research Design	The findings of this study have summarized and shortlisted the success factors in the two categories such as internal and external factors have caused to be influenced to delay of road construction in the Arab regions
	Deep, Banerjee, Dixit, & Vatin	2022		Critical Factors Influencing the Performance of Highway Projects: An Empirical Evaluation	Exploratory Factor	The analysis, it was identified that the factors were grouped under four categories: Execution constraints, Operational factors, Stakeholder and political constraints, Design Constraints.

Source: Researchers Compilation, 2022

Gap in Reviewed Related Literature

None of the studies reviewed was done in Enugu East and Isi-uzo local government Areas of Enugu state but many were conducted in Nigeria. These reviewed studies were not specifically conducted with relations to local government but were directly related to the objectives of the present study; primary health care, the feeder local roads and maintenance, and agricultural development. This area has been amazingly neglected until recently.

From observations established after the review of the previous studies the researcher observed that most of these reviewed studies conducted in Nigeria were not linked down to the grassroots level (local governments). This attracts the necessity of the starting point of the study; As such the present study tends to fill this gap through evaluation of the effect of Local Government Administration on rural development: A study of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government area in Enugu State.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted cross-sectional survey research design. This enabled the researcher to ascertain how the local government administration affected rural development in Enugu East and Isi – Uzo Local government areas of Enugu State.

Area of Study

The study was conducted in Enugu East and Isi-Uzo local government areas of Enugu State, Nigeria. Enugu East and Isi-Uzo are among the seventeen (17) local government areas in Enugu State.

Sources of Data

The data used in this study was sourced from primary and secondary sources:

Primary Data

- I. **Questionnaire:** Data were obtained from information supplied by the respondents to questions contained in the questionnaire distributed to them and the questions are framed in the most simple and unambiguous ways to enable respondents answer those questions accurately.
- II. **Secondary Data:** A lot of materials were used, especially for the theoretical frame work of the study which is obtained from textbooks, journals, magazines newspapers and internet materials

Population of the Study

The total population of the study was made up 2 selected local government areas in the state - Enugu East and Isi-Uzo local government area of Enugu State. Enugu east (308), and Isi-Uzo local government area (304) making a total population of six hundred and twelve (612). The study population in each of the local governments included the entire members of the local government staff and, executives of the town union leaders and selected individuals who were capable of knowing the effect of Local government administration in rural development in their communities.

Table 2: Population Distribution of the Selected 2 Two Lgas Under Study

S/N	LOCAL GOVT AREAS	No of the Executives of the town union	Local Govt staff	Total
1	Enugu East	10	298	308
2	Isi –Uzo	29	275	304
	Total	39	593	612

Source: Local government offices and the communities 2022

Sample Size Determination

The actual population was six hundred and twelve (612) staff and, executives of the town union and selected individuals who were capable of knowing the effect of Local government administration on rural development in their local communities using a stratified sampling method. To determine the adequate sample size, the researcher used Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu 2011).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N(pq)}{N(e)^2 + Z^2(pq)}$$

Where n = Sample Size
 N = The population
 p = Probability of success/proportion
 q = Probability of failure/proportion
 Z = Standard error of the mean
 e = Limit of tolerable error (or level of significance)
 N = 612
 p = .5
 q = (1 - .5) = .5
 Z = 95 percent = 1.96
 e = 0.05 percent

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 612 \times .5 \times .5}{612(0.03)^2 + (1.96)^2 \times .5 \times .5}$$

$$\frac{3.8416 \times 612 \times .25}{1.53 + 3.8416 \times .25}$$

$$= \frac{582.76}{2.59} = 225.00 \approx \underline{225}$$

Sampling Technique

Bowley's proportional allocation formula was used to allocate the sample size to the selected states and cities. It enhanced the distribution of questionnaire to the states cities. Bowley's proportional allocation formula is stated thus:

$$nh = \frac{nNh}{N}$$

n = The total sample size
 nh = proportional sample size
 Nh = population of each stratum
 N = The total population under study

Enugu East LGA	=	$\frac{308(225)}{612}$			
	=	$\frac{69300}{612}$	p(A)	=	113
Isi - Uzo LGA	=	$\frac{304(225)}{612}$			
	=	$\frac{68400}{612}$	p(A)	=	112 <u>225</u>

Method of Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The questionnaire items were structured using likert 5 points scale, and the values assigned to each option to measure the magnitude of the responses. Data was presented in tables, percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analysing the findings.

Scale

Strongly Agree (SA)	-	5
Agree (A)		4

Neutral(N)	-	3
Disagree (D)	-	2
Strongly Disagree (SD)	-	1

Decision Rule

If Mean ≥ 3.0, the respondents agree

If mean ≤3.0, the respondents disagree

Validity of the Instrument

The study tried out the entire process of the research study by distributing copies of the questionnaire to ascertain whether the questionnaire would satisfy what the study had in mind while constructing the questionnaire. The study used five residents of each of local government under study on whom questionnaire were administered for scoring. Resource persons in the communities including my supervisor also helped in the validation of the instrument. After the scoring by each respondent, the study evaluated each respondent scoring with his own simultaneously. The results obtained from the pilot group guided the study in restructuring the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability of a measure concerns its ability to produce similar results when repeated measurements are made under identical condition (Borden, 2008). A test-re-test method of reliability was adopted for this study in which 20 copies of 15 items questionnaire were distributed to other local government areas outside the study; five copies to each of three(3) local governments. The instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient testing tool (Refer to table 3.2a & 3.2b). The reliability result indicated 0.872, implying a high degree of items consistency.

Table 3: Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test

		N	%
Cases	Valid	15	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	To tal	15	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Table 3.2b Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha		Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.885		.872	15

SPSS 20.0 Output

Method of Data Analyses

Z - test, was used to test the hypotheses, determine the nature, and strength of the research variables.

Z –Test

$$Z = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

Where;

\bar{X} = Population mean

μ = Sample mean

σ = Standard deviation

n = Sample size

Data Presentation and Analysis

In this chapter, data relating to the study were presented, analyzed and interpreted. However, this section commenced with the background information of the respondents.

Data Presentation

The effect of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government councils on the enhancement of primary Health care in their council areas

Table 4: Responses to Research Question One on the Effect of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government Councils on the Enhancement of Primary Health Care in Their Council Areas

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 D	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	DECISIO N
1	There is urgent pre-hospital treatment provided by the local authority	600	136	72	32	28	868	3.91	1.440	Agree
		120	34	24	16	28	222			
		54.1	15.3	10.8	7.2	12.6	100%			
2	The local authority has emergency provision for stabilization for serious illness and injuries	575	124	78	44	28	849	3.82	1.465	Agree
		115	31	26	22	28	222			
		51.8	14.0	11.7	9.9	12.6	100%			
3	There is emergency vehicle in the area that facilitates immediate health services.	45	572	18	26	302	963	3.73	1.307	Agree
		72	88	17	20	25	222			
		32.4	39.6	7.7	9.0	11.3	100%			
4	Access to life savings medical care in the rural areas is provided in the communities.	525	160	81	52	24	842	3.79	1.415	Agree
		105	40	27	26	24	222			
		47.3	18.0	12.2	11.7	10.8	100%			
5	The local authorities provides clinic in the autonomous communities to reduce underserved health care.	255	460	45	30	26	816	3.68	1.234	Agree
		51	115	15	15	26	222			
		23.0	51.8	6.8	6.8	11.7	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.78	1.3722	
								6		

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The table above shows that the mean score of the questionnaire items 1-5 are 3.91, 3.82, 3.73, 3.79 and 3.68 respectively. All the 5 means scores are above the decision level of 2.50. in addition, the grand means is 3.78 which is also above the decision level of 2.50 therefore, the result is that Enugu East and Isi-uzo LGAs to a great extent enhanced primary healthcare in their council areas.

The effect of the performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas in the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas.

Table 5: Responses to Research Question One on the Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government Council Areas in the Construction and Maintenance of Local Feeder Roads in Their Council Areas.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	DECISIO
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		N
1	The local roads are maintained in the areas.	345 69 31.1	396 99 44.6	48 16 7.2	28 14 6.3	24 24 10.8	841 222 100%	3.79	1.253	Agree
2	There is settlement of property rights relations during road construction.	295 59 26.6	416 104 46.8	36 12 5.4	46 23 10.4	24 24 10.8	817 222 100%	3.68	1.270	Agree
3	Improved access road in the rural areas of the local government provides better availability of farm outputs.	315 63 28.4	320 80 36.0	78 26 11.7	50 25 11.3	28 28 12.6	791 222 100%	3.56	1.343	Agree
4	The local authorities provided better connectivity of roads that enhances health and financial services.	250 50 22.5	444 111 50.0	15 5 2.3	46 23 10.4	33 33 14.9	788 222 100%	3.55	1.344	Agree
5	The improved roads by the local authorities facilitated effective public services and functionaries in the rural areas.	250 50 22.5	404 101 45.5	27 9 4.1	46 23 10.4	39 39 17.6	766 222 100%	3.45	1.403	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.60	1.3226	
								6		

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The table above shows that the mean score of the questionnaire items 1-5 are 3.79, 3.68, 3.56, 3.55 and 3.45 respectively. All the 5 means scores are above the decision level of 2.50. In addition, the grand means is 3.60 which is also above the decision level of 2.50 therefore, the result is that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo LGAs to a great extent enhanced construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas.

The extent of agricultural development by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas

Table 6: Responses to research question one on the extent of agricultural development by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 D	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The local authorities have aided in agricultural productions in the area.	520 104 46.8	204 51 23.0	33 11 5.0	46 23 10.4	33 33 10.4	836 222 100%	3.77	1.492	Agree
2	The local government assists in identifying and analyzing community problems in the agricultural sector.	350 70 31.5	340 85 38.3	33 11 5.0	46 23 10.4	35 33 14.9	802 222 100%	3.61	1.406	Agree
3	The local authorities help in the tractors and other skills in the area.	240 48 21.6	476 119 53.6	33 11 5.0	46 23 10.4	21 21 9.5	816 222 100%	3.69	1.197	Agree
4	The local authorities help on the training of farmers to improve efficiency	630 126 56.8	212 53 23.9	42 14 6.3	30 15 6.8	14 14 6.3	928 222 100%	4.18	1.201	Agree
5	The provision of seeds for farming are done with assistance of local authorities	510 102 45.9	292 73 32.9	39 13 5.9	40 20 9.0	14 14 6.3	895 222 100%	4.03	1.205	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							2.856	1.3002	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The table above shows that the mean score of the questionnaire items 1-5 are 3.77, 3.61, 3.69, 4.18 and 4.03 respectively. All the 5 means scores are above the decision level of 2.50. In addition, the grand means is 3.85 which is also above the decision level of 2.50 therefore, the result is that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo LGAs to a great extent enhanced agricultural development.

Test of Hypotheses

Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas have not contributed significantly to enhancement of primary health care in their council areas

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		There is urgent pre-hospital treatment provided the local authority	The local authority has emergency provision for stabilization for serious illness and injuries	There is emergency vehicle in the area that facilitates immediate health services.	Access to life savings medical care in the rural areas is provided in the communities.	The local authorities provides clinic in the autonomous communities to reduce underserved health care.
N		222	222	222	222	222
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.541	.518	.471	.473	.498
	Positive	.126	.126	.113	.108	.117
	Negative	-.541	-.518	-.471	-.473	-.498
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.054	7.718	7.014	7.047	7.416
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – values ranging from $.265 < .374$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had contributed significantly to enhancement of primary health care in their council areas

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $.265 < .374$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97% level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had contributed significantly to enhancement of primary health care in their council areas

Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas has no significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		The local roads are maintained in the areas	There is settlement of property rights relations during road construction.	Improved access road in the rural areas of the local government provides better availability of farm outputs.	The local authorities provided better connectivity of roads that enhances health and financial services.	The improved roads by the local authorities facilitated effective public services and functionaries in the rural areas.
N		222	222	222	222	222
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.507	.484	.394	.475	.430
	Positive	.108	.108	.126	.149	.176
	Negative	-.507	-.484	-.394	-.475	-.430
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.551	7.215	5.873	7.081	6.410
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – values ranging from $.252 < .361$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents that performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $.252 < .361$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97% level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas

There is no significant development in agricultural by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas

Discussion of Findings

The effect of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government councils on the enhancement of primary Healthcare in their council areas

In the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- values ranging from $-.265 < .374$, against the critical Z- value of $.000$. The study concluded that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had contributed significantly to enhancement of primary health care in their council areas. Primary health care helps to promote health, prevent illness and can address most of an individual's health needs throughout their life. It also helps to identify, treat, and refer patients to specialists when appropriate. Access to most healthcare services in Nigeria is often through the private sector and this applies to primary healthcare services as well. Unfortunately, most Nigerians still fail to access primary health care services. The prevailing issue is the lack of access to finance and the cost barrier they perceive. Other reasons include distance, lack of awareness of the availability of services. On the supply side, the reasons are the attitudes of healthcare workers and poorly equipped facilities or the legacy of these which does not make it easy to trust. Therefore the result of the test of hypotheses one shows that if the private sector can provide health care in Nigeria that the government council if in full support to the health center will to a great extent enhance the performance of the health care sector in the local government areas.

Performance Of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government Areas Had Significant Effect on the Construction and Maintenance of Local Feeder Roads in their Council Areas

In the result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z- values ranging from $.252 < .361$ against the critical Z- value of $.000$ which implies that performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas. The result of the hypotheses two show that the increasing rate of bad roads, poor constructed roads and potholes seen in Nigeria roads mainly in the rural areas is as a result of poor governance and neglect of the government to its duty. In support of the hypotheses Ilori, (N.d) proposed that it is now universally recognized that in order to overcome the rigidities inherent in a developing country, the state must play a positive role in infrastructure investment. It cannot afford to play the role of a spectator. The development of infrastructure entails large investments, which are beyond the capacity of individual or groups of private enterprise in such countries. Not only this, investment benefits of infrastructure are realisable only over a long period. It therefore, devolves on the State to provide public utilities.

There was Significant Development in Agricultural by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local Government Areas

In the result of hypothesis three, the calculated Z- values ranging from $.297 < .362$ against the critical Z- value of $.000$. The study concluded that the agricultural development had positive effect in Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas. Many governments in developing countries attempt to foster agricultural development and innovation by setting up funding facilities, extension programs, and research centers and by subsidizing private-sector and farm activities through fiscal measures. However, when trying to manage complex innovation processes involving many and different actors, governments sometimes find it difficult to design effective interventions and therefore end up supporting and managing only the public research and extension organizations that directly depend upon them. Nwalieji H., & Igbokwe E.M., (2013) asserts that it is observed that LG in Nigeria has not performed to expectation, thereby recorded abysmal level of inefficiency and ineffectiveness. LGs should look inwards for improved IGR in order to make them financially self-reliant; linkages between LGC and ADP and other agricultural projects and programmes should be strengthened in order to foster development; bottom-up approach should be adopted in the linkage between LG and farmers for effective rural community involvement and participation in major decisions that affecting them

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of the study include the following:

- I. Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had contributed significantly to enhancement of primary health care in their council areas, $Z(95, n = 222) = -.265 < .374, p > 0.05$.

- II. Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas had significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads in their council areas, $Z(95, n = 222) = .252 < .361, p < 0.05$.
- III. there was significant development in agricultural by Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government areas, $Z(95, n = 222) = .297 < .362, p < 0.05$

Conclusion

The study concluded that Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas had contributed significantly on the primary Health care in their council areas while Performance of Enugu East and Isi-Uzo Local government council areas had significant effect on the construction and maintenance of local feeder roads and agricultural development in their council areas. The local government in Nigeria was established for the purpose of rendering services and supplying amenities to the people in both rural and urban areas according to the document establishing the local government reforms in 1976. By extension, the same conditions apply to local governments in Enugu state which was created on 27th August 1991. Federal government cannot perform all the activities of the rural areas by themselves, but this can only be done by the people elected for that purpose. This does not stop the federal government from implementing their roles by providing all the social amenities, such as construction of roads, provision of pipe borne water, hospital, good education for youths, stadium, electricity and museum etc.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proffered:

- I. The local government authorities should be more proactive and ensure that emergency medical services need to be attended to by providing budget for health care of the people in their local governments.
- II. The government official with corrupt mentality history should not be giving chance to handle responsibilities rather; people with better integrity should be given the position to occupy government positions that are sensitive and could help achieve economic development objectives especially the provision of roads in the rural areas.
- III. Government should improve on the manpower by equipping and employing more hands on agricultural development to enhance the adequate coverage of the various areas and state and more effort should be in place towards tackling the challenges facing the frontline LGAs.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study on effect of local government administration on rural developments after it reviews and findings would contribute to the existing knowledge in this research area that the local government. Local government is responsible for a range of vital services for people and businesses in defined areas. Local self-government offers the best opportunity to the people to bring knowledge, interest and enthusiasm to bear on the solution of their own local problem and as such the government administrations in charge of the rural areas should ensure that they provide this rural areas with the required infrastructures which will not only help in enhancing the system of living in the rural areas but will also help to reduce rural-urban migration, unemployment, robbery and all sorts of bad behavior which would occur as a result of poor living.

Suggestions for Further Studies

- I. Government spending on infrastructure and economic development in Nigeria
- II. Government Expenditures on Education, Health, and Infrastructure: A review to economic development

References

- Abdulrahman, D. (2013). *Overcoming Nigeria's Security Challenges*, University of Massachusetts Publishers, Boston, USA
- Adenike, A. A. (2017). *Local government tax mobilization and utilization in Nigeria: problems and prospects*. Retrieved from <http://visar.csustan.edu/aaba/Adedokun.pdf>
- Agbeboh G. U. & Osabuohien-Irabor O. (2013) Empirical analysis of road traffic accidents: A case study of Kogi State, North-Central Nigeria *International Journal of Physical Sciences* 8(40), 1923-1933.
- Anorom, A. (2012). Philosophy and Society. *African Journal for Culture, (AJC)* 2(1): 101-115
- Asaga P.M., Kroeger A., & Airiohuodion P. E. (2019). Needs assessment of emergency medical and rescue services in Abuja/Nigeria and environs. *BMC Emergency Medicine* 19(78). Retrieved from <https://bmccemergmed.Bio medcentral.com/ articles/10.1186/s12873-019-0291-9>
- Ashley, D. (2020). *What is local government? definition, responsibilities & challenges*. Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-local-government-definition-responsibilities-challenges.html>
- Bennett, T.H. Holloway, D.P. and Farrington (2008). *The effectiveness of Neighbourhood watch in reducing crime, campbell systematic reviews*. Retrieved from https://eucpn.org/sites/default/files/document/files/2._the_effects_of_neighbourhood_watch_in_reducing_crime.pdf
- Boskovic, Z.V. & Tepsa, I.V. (2015). *The significance of roads for the development of region*. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/a/osi/eecyvt/v4y2015p789-793.html>
- Dangmei T. & Sing U. (2018). An Empirical Assessment of Primary Health Care Quality Services and Its Effect on Patient Satisfaction in Anuppur District, Madhya Pradesh. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 4(1)
- Deep S., Banerjee S., Dixit, S. & Vatin, N.I. (2022). Critical Factors Influencing the Performance of Highway Projects: An Empirical Evaluation. *Buildings* (12), 849.<https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12060849>
- Espinosa-Gonzalez A.B., Delaney B.C., Marti J., & Darzi A. (2019). The impact of governance in primary health care delivery: a systems thinking approach with a European panel. *Health Research Policy and Systems* (17) 65
- Gyanden, P. K. (2015). The role of extension services in reduction of biomass burning in Okpokwu Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Conference: International Conference on Latest Trends in Food, Biological & Ecological Sciences (ICLTBE'15) Oct. 11-12, Dubai (UAE)
- Haseeb, J. (2017). *Classification of roads-arterial collector, local roads*. Retrieved from <https://www.aboutcivil.org/road-classification-system.html>
- Idahosa, S.A. & Nchuchuwe, F. (2005). *Local government finances in Nigeria: issues in generation, utilization, accountability and service delivery*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328581546>
- Idogwu A. A., Ogunlade S., Nmeregini C.S., & Akinpelu A. A. (2018). The Role of Demand-Responsive Transportation System in Road Traffic Accidents in part of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria *The Scientific World Journal* 108(5):1-17.
- Igbuzor, O. (2010). Strategic Oriented Policing in Nigeria (*Paper Presented at the Police Service Commission Biennial Retreat on the Challenges of Policing in a Democratic Society in the 21st Century and Beyond at Uyo, Akwa-Ibom State from 1st -4th November, 2010*).
- Ilori, I. (N.d). The role of Government in the Development of Basic Infrastructure <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/out/Publications/reports/occasionalpapers/RD/2004/Jos-02-3.pdf>
- Jonathan, E. (2019). *Emergency response in the city of Enugu a qualitative exploratory single case study*. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/e1c7558f1f69283b2a2da53688173586/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Lendra, Wlbowo & Hatmoko (2020). Literature Review on Energy Consumption in Road Construction Projects Literature Review on Energy Consumption in Road Construction Projects. 2nd International Conference on Sustainable. *Infrastructure Journal of Physics Conference Series* 1625(1)
- Local government finance in Nigeria. A case study of Iwo local government area of Osun State. *International Journal of Politics and Good Governance*, 6, (6.1), Quarter 1, 1-29.
- Makama J. G., Iribhogbe P., Ameh E. A. (2015). Overcrowding of accident & emergency units: is it a growing concern in Nigeria? *African Health Sciences* 15 (2) 457-465
- Nwalieji H., & Igbokwe E.M. (2013). Role of Local Governments in Agricultural Development in Nigeria: A Review. *Journal of Agricultural Extension* 15 (2) 1-10
- Nwanne, T. F. I. (2015). Effect of Tax Policy on the Expenditure of Local Government Councils in Imo State. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research* 3 (12) 79-97

- Obinna, C.A. (2017). Revenue generation in Enugu state local governments, Nigeria: an assessment of tax contractors. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 5(1): 236-247.
- Oduola, S. Olasunkanmi, Sawaneh, B. and Ogunbela, G. (2019). *Revenue generation in Lagelu local government area of Oyo state: a correlate of tax mobilization and utilization*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332531242>
- Ohakwe J., Iwueze I., & Chikezie D.C. (2011). Analysis of Road Traffic Accidents in Nigeria: A Case Study of Obinze/Nekede/Iheagwa Road in Imo State, Southeastern, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Applied Sciences* 4(2):166-175
- Olorungbemi, S.T. (2015), Revenue generation and local government administration in Nigeria (1999-2007): the case of Ijumu local government area of Kogi State. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(10): 137-15
- Omodero C. O., Ekwe M., & Ihendinihu J. (2018)The Impact of Internally Generated Revenue on Economic Development in Nigeria. *Accounting and Finance Research* 7(2):166
- Osain, M. (2011). The Nigeria health care system: need for integrating adequate medical intelligence and surveillance systems. *Journal of Pharmacy & BioAllied Sciences*, 3(4): 470-478
- Oserei K.M., & Uddin G.E. (2019). The myth and reality of government expenditure on primary health care in Nigeria: Way forward to inclusive growth. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340223000_The_myth_and_reality_of_government_expenditure_on_primary_health_care_in_Nigeria_Way_forward_to_inclusive_growth
- Ozohu-S., and Paul, C. (2016). Local government administration in Nigeria: the search for relevance *Commonwealth Journal of Local Governance*
- Packard, R. (2016). *A History of Global Health*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins. pp. 227–229.
- Palliser, D.M. (2020). *Local government*. Retrieved from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/social-sciences-and-law/political-science-and-government/political-science-terms-and-concepts/local-government>
- Scharticles, O. (2014). *Enhancing Local Government Effectiveness in Nigeria*. Administrative Democrat, 13(10): 7
- Snooks HA, Anthony R & Chatters R. (2017). Systematic review of literature on effects of interventions by emergency medical staff for older people who fall. Southampton (UK): *NIHR Journals Library; Health Technology Assessment, 21.13. ch2*
- Suleiman S.A., Abul B.B., & Setyawan W. (2020). The Empirical Review of Critical Success Factors on the Causes of Delay in Road Constructions Projects in the GCC Countries. *Australian Finance & Banking Review* 4 (2) 15-36
- Ugwuoke, B. C. and Attamah, C. O. (2019). Linkages between the Agricultural Development Programme and the Local Government Agricultural Department in Southeast, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension, Electronic Journals Service (EJS)*, 23 (1)
- Ukwayi & Okpa (2017). *Socio-demographic factors affecting the safety of lives and properties in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria*. Press
- WHO (2021). *Primary health care*<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/primary-health-care>